

Social Media Strategy (Revised)

V3.2

Author: Institute for Methods Innovation

Contact: Daniela Martin (daniela@methodsinnovation.org)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 776816

Social media strategy for external communications

Based on the communication goals and analysis of the identified target audiences for Project Ô, a strategic communication plan for social media was developed to guide project communication and dissemination after IMI joined as a project partner in RP2. The narrative of this document starts with an assessment of the pre-IMI status of the project's social media accounts, followed by an analysis of similar accounts. It proposes a detailed work plan for standing up the social media accounts and building an audience based on key messages, target audiences and communication channels. This document, prepared by IMI, was also designed to allow us to evaluate our efforts during the implementation of the social media strategy to see if we are generating the desired impact. This strategy was presented to Work Package leader Professor Alexander Gerber for his feedback prior to implementation by IMI.

Please note that the material below is future-oriented because it was drafted prior to the project's main effort with social media (which began after IMI joined as a partner in RP2).

IMI's Social Media Strategy

Social media status prior to IMI joining the project

A social media audit creates a clear picture of current (pre-IMI) social efforts, with the aim of revealing gaps and opportunities that highlight the best ways to improve results. In this particular case, the social media accounts have been inactive since February 2020 due to staffing challenges at HSRW, and the only relevant starting information available for the audit is the number of followers. This will help us evaluate progress once this strategy is implemented.

Table 1. Social media status¹

Platform	Handle	Followers
Twitter	@EUProjectO	365
Facebook	/euprojectoeu	44
YouTube	@euprojecto	0
LinkedIn	/eu-project-ô/	0

¹ As of January 11th, 2022, when IMI's work on social media commenced in earnest.

Benchmarking

While developing a social media strategy, it is useful to analyse what other similar or comparable projects are already doing right or wrong (and with what effect on their communication outcomes). The goal of this benchmark is to understand from external examples what is working and what needs to be improved in our social media activities.

The table below contains examples of projects from the IC4TWater cluster of EU-funded projects, where Project Ô is also located. Even with a benchmark comparison of the ICT4Water cluster of EU-funded projects, there are clearly vast differences in the level of social media output and the degree of uptake from audiences. This highlights the importance of project-specific strategies to boost visibility and impact. The table indicates the main indicators of social media reach and the nature of their social media messaging:

Table 2. IC4TWater social media benchmarking

Project	Social media	Types of posts	Examples
Aqua3s	<p>Twitter:</p> <p>@aqua3seu</p> <p>188 followers</p> <p>151 tweets since 2019</p> <p>LinkedIn:</p> <p>166 followers</p>	<p>Retweets, short texts with emojis, links and images.</p> <p>Content focuses on events and explanations of how their technology works.</p> <p>Posts focusing on events (short description and an image).</p>	<p>The screenshot shows a tweet from the account 'aqua3S' (@aqua3seu). The text of the tweet asks 'What are the 3 stages of #wastewater treatment?' and provides an explanatory text: 'Each stage purifies #water to a higher level. In some applications, only 1 or 2 stages are necessary. Read more buff.ly/3ncnCBI'. Below the text is an aerial photograph of a wastewater treatment plant with several large circular tanks. The tweet is from 'Trilateral Research y 4 más'.</p>

<p>AquaSPICE</p>	<p>Twitter:</p> <p>@AquaSPICE1</p> <p>120 followers</p> <p>44 tweets since November 2020</p>	<p>Short texts with emojis, links and images.</p> <p>Mainly original posts with EU news related to the topic, events, public workshops and explanation of technical processes.</p>	<p>AquaSPICE @AquaSPICE1</p> <p>Did you know that the Port of #Antwerp is the leading #European oil & chemical hotspot in the 🇪🇺 ?</p> <p>A month ago, @AquaSPICE1 partners joined the CS#3-Antwerp case Workshop to discuss the 2 subcases in this location ➡ buff.ly/2QWshSD Stay tuned 4 more #WorkshopWeekly</p> <p>Traducir Tweet</p> <p>CS#3 - ANTWERP CASE Workshop</p> <p>BASF y 3 más</p>
<p>Blue-RoSES</p>	<p>Twitter:</p> <p>@BlueRoSEsproj</p> <p>50 followers</p> <p>24 tweets since December 2019</p> <p>LinkedIn:</p> <p>22 followers</p> <p>Instagram:</p> <p>@blue_roses_project</p>	<p>Medium-length texts without emojis.</p> <p>Each text is accompanied by links and images (pictures of virtual meetings, infographics, etc.).</p> <p>Mainly original posts focused on the progress and activities of the project.</p> <p>One post per week. Focus is on the progress, activities and events of the project.</p> <p>Same images used in Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn with longer text descriptions.</p>	<p>Blue-RoSES @BlueRoSEsproj</p> <p>Fascinated with marine robots, but wonder what UMV, AUV, ASV or ROV stand for? We've assembled an infographic to clarify these acronyms and provide an overview of marine robot categories.</p> <p>#infographic #roboticsforall #sustainability #environmental @cinea_eu @EUgreenddeal</p> <p>Traducir Tweet</p> <p>Marine robots Unmanned marine vehicles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> AUV (Autonomous Underwater Vehicles): Underwater, Acoustic communication, Torpedo-shaped, Energy efficient, Long range operations, Poor interaction with the environment. ASV (Autonomous Surface Vehicles): Surface, Wave-powered or propeller driven, Partial or fully autonomous control. ROV (Remotely Operated Vehicles): Underwater, Tether for power supply & communications, Short range long-time operations, Interactions with the environment also with robotic arms. <p>3:40 a. m. · 17 may. 2021 · Twitter Web App</p>

	<p>8 followers</p> <p>17 posts</p> <p>Facebook:</p> <p>/BlueRosesProject</p> <p>186 likes</p>	<p>Same images as Instagram and longer text.</p>	<p>blue_roses_project</p> <p>blue_roses_project Monday News: SWAMP exhibited at the Venice Boat Show!</p> <p>Capitalising on the experience gained in the Blue RoSES project, the team CNR - INM is going to develop in the frame of the Interreg Italy-Croatia InnovaMARE project, two prototype SWAMP ASVs (+ a set of scientific and technological kits). As part of InnovaMARE, one of the prototype SWAMP ASV has been exhibited at the Venice Boat Show in the headquarters of the Cnr-Ismar Istituto di Scienze Marine.</p> <p>Stay tuned for the 'off-the-records' video, showcasing a basic system</p> <p>2 Me gusta</p> <p>7 DE JUNIO</p> <p>Añade un comentario... Publicar</p>
<p>BWaterSmart Project</p>	<p>Twitter:</p> <p>@B_WaterSmart</p> <p>243 followers</p> <p>40 tweets since September 2020</p>	<p>Short text without emojis, sometimes without images as well.</p> <p>Retweets from other similar accounts.</p> <p>Context focuses on the activities of the project such as meetings, published papers and events.</p>	<p>B-WaterSmart @B_WaterSmart</p> <p>B-WaterSmart Living Labs across Europe develop sustainable and efficient solutions for water use #watersmartness #circulareconomy</p> <p>Traducir Tweet</p> <p>Living Labs across Europe develop sustainable and efficient ... Your Content Goes Here Living Labs across Europe develop sustainable and efficient solutions for water use Climate ... b-watersmart.eu</p> <p>4:13 a. m. · 1 abr. 2021 · Twitter Web App</p> <p>3 Retweets 1 Citar Tweet 6 Me gusta</p>
<p>Digital Water City</p>	<p>Twitter:</p> <p>@digitalwater_eu</p> <p>514 followers</p> <p>367 tweets since July 2018</p> <p>LinkedIn:</p>	<p>Short texts, minimum use of emojis, proper use of hashtags and links.</p> <p>Content focuses on the activities and events, its members and the impact of the project.</p> <p>When they're not using photographs, they follow design templates such as the example on the right.</p>	<p>digital-water.city @digitalwater_eu</p> <p>How #DWH2020 Synergy group can strengthen the impact of digitalisation in the #water sector @CaradotNico explained how 5 H2020 projects strive for managing our water resources through #digitalisation at #FIWARESmartFest. Want to know more? 🤖 digital-water.city/news/synergy-g...</p> <p>Traducir Tweet</p> <p>DW2020 is all about using synergies between digital water projects and avoid reinventing the wheel: key challenges are coherent data models, sensors integration and business development</p> <p>Nico Caradot Digital-water.city coordinator Kompetenzzentrum Wasser</p> <p>NAIADES y 9 más</p> <p>11:53 a. m. · 9 jun. 2021 · Twitter Web App</p>

	<p>820 followers</p>	<p>The content is very similar to Twitter. At least 1 post per week.</p>	
<p>Monocle</p>	<p>Twitter:</p> <p>@MONOCLE_H2 020</p> <p>536 followers</p> <p>200 tweets since November 2017</p>	<p>Short text descriptions accompanied by images.</p> <p>No use of emojis.</p> <p>Mainly original posts.</p> <p>Content focuses on the project's technologies.</p>	

<p>NAIADES</p>	<p>Twitter:</p> <p>@naiadesproject</p> <p>257 followers</p> <p>152 tweets since August 2019</p> <p>Facebook:</p> <p>/naiadesproject</p> <p>161 likes</p> <p>LinkedIn:</p> <p>66 members</p>	<p>Medium-length texts, minimum use of emojis.</p> <p>Proper use of hashtags and links.</p> <p>Every tweet is usually accompanied by an image.</p> <p>Content focuses on their technology and events.</p> <p>Long texts, minimum use of emojis and hashtags.</p> <p>Context focuses on events, world news related to the project and explanations of their technologies.</p> <p>Profile is set up as a closed group.</p>	
-----------------------	--	--	--

<p>Zero Brine</p>	<p>Twitter: @zero_brine_ 922 followers 981 tweets since November 2017</p> <p>LinkedIn: 442 followers</p> <p>YouTube: 16 videos 396 total views</p>	<p>Medium-length texts, minimum use of emojis.</p> <p>Proper use of hashtags and links.</p> <p>Retweets from similar accounts.</p> <p>Content focuses mainly on events, activities and the technology of the project.</p> <p>One post every two weeks focusing on the technology and events of the project.</p> <p>Zero Brine’s videos are located in a playlist within REVOLVE’s YouTube channel, alongside with videos of other EU projects related to topics such as water, energy, forests, mobility, cities and circular economy.</p>	<p>ZERO BRINE @zero_brine_</p> <p>At one of the EU's largest #silica producers, #ZERBRINE is demonstrating #CircularEconomy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🏭 60% less sodium sulphate discharged to the environment ⚡ 72% energy savings 💧 Water reduction by 1 million cubic meters annually <p>Read our press release here: mailchi.mp/3ad8c2143ce2/a...</p> <p>Traducir Tweet</p> <p>Eurecat y 9 más</p>
--------------------------	---	--	--

Target audiences

Two main target audiences have been identified from our preliminary stakeholder mapping: technical communities with an interest in water sustainability and general, non-technical public audiences that may be affected by water sustainability initiatives and projects such as Project Ô. Each one of these broad audience categories comprises specific stakeholder groups with different levels of awareness, understanding, engagement and knowledge of the topics concerning Project Ô. A differentiated view of the target audiences is important to ensure that communication approaches are tailored in a way that will be effective. However, the two broad categories of technical vs. non-technical audiences help to clarify the key distinction between communications aimed at professionals in the water sector or the general public.

Table 3. Target audiences

Target audience	Specific stakeholders' characteristics
Technical communities	<p>Policymakers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May understand the basics of some of the technical aspects but not a high level of detail. • May be former engineers, now in a policy-making role and therefore seeking technological knowledge. • May be public-facing/accountable for decisions, so need to back up decisions with credible sources of knowledge. <p>Industry or Private-Sector</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May implement and use the technologies. • May work for private-sector companies looking to exploit the technology as a means for increasing shareholder value or improving public perception, e.g. utilities or factories with sewage. <p>Academic researchers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academics and scholars involved in water-related research. • May work for universities, scientific institutions, consultancies, NGOs, and/or research funding organisations.
General, non-technical public audiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May have no background knowledge to understand what the project is and the implications it could have for them. • May already be aware that water reuse could affect their everyday lives or local communities. • May reside near the demsites and/or in towns that have not yet adopted these kinds of technologies. • May use green spaces, such as community parks that are impacted by poor quality or undrinkable water. • May recognise the benefits for themselves or their community of more reliable, mobile and scalable water sources.

Audience profiles

An audience profile is the visualisation of a "person" representing an aggregated idea of our audiences and their motivations for engaging on social media. Audience profiles help clarify demographics (i.e., age, education, etc), behaviours, goals, challenges, interests, and more. A profile guides further development of messaging for social media content by targeting specific audience characteristics. A key question for content and visual development is whether it will resonate with a particular person in these target audience profiles.

The following profiles are a starting point and may change over time depending on the results of social media and stakeholder analytics.

Table 4. Overview of audience profiles

Technical Community	General Public
<p data-bbox="472 825 578 852">Profile 1</p> <p data-bbox="951 1066 1247 1094">Small Business Manager</p>	
<p data-bbox="472 1129 578 1157">Profile 2</p> <p data-bbox="922 1402 1276 1430">Recent High School Graduate</p>	

Technical Community Profiles

Profile 1: Water Systems Engineer

The first profile is represented by someone in her mid-40s who is a highly educated engineer, working in the private-sector for water treatment. She manages a team that maintains and improves water treatment systems, works on a range of high-profile projects, and dedicates a significant amount of time to keep up-to-date with the latest research and innovation available in the water treatment sector. She tends to gain information by attending professional conferences and workshops, talking to peers in the field of engineering and reading published academic journals.

Twitter and LinkedIn are her preferred social networks to connect and share information with other professionals working in the water treatment sector. She shares highlights of her work irregularly, but she is part of several LinkedIn groups with professionals and peers that share local updates on technologies and innovative practices.

Figure 1. Technical community profile: Water Systems Engineer

</p>	<p>Professional responsibilities:</p> <p>Manage a team of engineers, improve efficiency of water treatment systems</p> <p>Professional objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Make water treatment systems more efficient. ● Find materials and source innovative practices to reduce costs and limit waste byproducts. ● Stay informed of the technologies available in the water sector. <p>Preferred sources of information:</p> <p>Published scientific journals, professional conferences and workshops, informal conversations with practitioners, social media for professional networking, technology fairs.</p> <p>Preferred methods of communication</p> <p>Face-to-face, phone, email, social media</p>
--	---

Profile 2: Policymaker in EU Parliament

The second profile is represented by a policymaker in his mid-50s from a rural community in Spain. He now serves in the European parliament after a career at Amnesty International, where he was an advocate for human rights legislation in neighbouring EU countries.

His work involves regular meetings with representatives from private industry, community groups and non-governmental organisations to gain insights for his legislative agenda, which still prioritises sustainable development goals around food and water security. For this reason, he frequently interfaces with other policymakers and sits on sustainability committees that deal with water supply and sanitation.

He stays interested in the innovations coming from university research and private sector (i.e., local utilities and water suppliers), and wants to stay current on water treatment systems that will address water supply challenges. He prefers to review policy briefs first and then follow up directly with scientists or engineers to better understand any technical information.

Twitter and LinkedIn are his preferred social networks to promote legislation and learn about interesting research and innovative technologies. He will engage with projects that support his legislative agenda and focus on circular water economy.

Figure 2. Technical community profile: Policymaker in EU Parliament

</p>	<p>Professional responsibilities: Draft and promote legislation, meet with industry, represent constituents, review policy briefs, stay aware of innovative technologies</p> <p>Professional objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Improve the life quality of his constituents. ● Be properly informed for legislative procedures. ● Take scientific advice into account when making important decisions. <p>Preferred sources of information: Policy briefs, printed media, conferences, peer-to-peer conversations, social media.</p> <p>Preferred methods of communication: Face-to-face, phone, email, social media</p>
--	--

General Public, Non-technical Profiles

Profile 3: Small Business Manager

The third profile is represented by a small business manager in his mid-40s living in Croatia's capital. After living in the city for so many years, he has generally positive views about his local water supply and usually drinks water straight from the tap. While he is unfamiliar with water treatment technology specifically, he is interested to learn about innovations that reduce pollution and improve clean drinking water.

He does not see his relationship with nature as any integral part of who he is, but he would agree that he has a responsibility to help protect the environment. He has worked for the same small business for 16 years and did not complete a university degree. If asked, he would say that prioritising people's jobs is more important than the environment. With his country being outside of the EU, he expresses doubt in the European Commission's ability to help his country or do what is right for his community.

He uses Google when searching for information and will use Facebook to stay connected with family and friends.

Figure 3. General public profile: Small Business Manager

<div data-bbox="396 1098 609 1304" data-label="Image"> </div> <p data-bbox="370 1325 630 1381">Job Title Local Business Manager</p> <p data-bbox="331 1419 669 1514">Level of Education Educational qualification below university degree</p> <p data-bbox="410 1549 589 1625">Social Networks </p>	<p data-bbox="711 1115 1024 1140">Professional responsibilities:</p> <p data-bbox="711 1161 1308 1236">Maintain his business on a day-to-day basis, look after his employees</p> <p data-bbox="711 1274 971 1299">Professional objectives:</p> <ul data-bbox="760 1325 1284 1388" style="list-style-type: none"> ● Keep jobs for himself and his employees ● Keep good relationships with his community <p data-bbox="711 1415 1078 1440">Preferred sources of information:</p> <p data-bbox="711 1461 1289 1486">Talking to community, meetings with local authorities</p> <p data-bbox="711 1514 1133 1539">Preferred methods of communication:</p> <p data-bbox="711 1560 1247 1585">Face-to-face, social media, text messaging, phone</p>
---	---

Profile 4: Recent High School Graduate

The last profile is represented by a young adult, recently graduated from high school in Israel. She has a generally negative view about her local water supply, seeing it as dirty and risky. For this reason, she almost always drinks from bottled water but will drink filtered water when it is available.

She is completely unfamiliar with water treatment technology and may feel confused or bored by technical information; however, she is also hopeful that innovations from modern science might someday solve environmental problems, such as reducing pollution, keeping lakes and rivers clean and improving drinking water. The environment is important, but she does not feel there is anything she can do personally to help protect the environment. Additionally, with her country being outside of the EU, she doubts the European Commission would do what is right for her community.

She prefers Instagram and TikTok to share stories and highlights from her life. She uses Google when searching for information and will use Facebook messenger to stay connected with family and friends.

Figure 4. General public profile: Recent High School Graduate

<div data-bbox="420 1052 621 1283" data-label="Image"> </div> <p data-bbox="451 1335 586 1392">Age Young Adult</p> <p data-bbox="345 1434 691 1524">Level of Education No Formal Qualification: Recent High School Student</p> <p data-bbox="396 1562 634 1646">Social Networks </p>	<p data-bbox="729 1073 1252 1171">Professional responsibilities: Prepare for college, help cook and look after her younger siblings</p> <p data-bbox="729 1199 1138 1371">Professional objectives:</p> <ul data-bbox="777 1251 1138 1371" style="list-style-type: none"> ● Get into a good university ● Travel outside of her country ● Become more independent <p data-bbox="729 1409 865 1482">Preferred methods of communication: Social media</p> <p data-bbox="729 1524 1157 1598">Preferred sources of information: Google, Browsing Instagram and TikTok</p>
--	--

Audience-specific Goals and Objectives

A key part of a social media strategy is setting targeted goals to develop content with a clear direction. Identifying clear, specific goals will help us get the most out of social media. The following goals are based on WP8. However, it is worth noting that WP9 is primarily responsible for communication with technical communities.

Technical Communities

The main objective is to raise awareness of Project Ô technologies and to build trust in them. This will be achieved through content posted on Facebook, Twitter, YouTube and LinkedIn.

Table 5. *Communications Goals for Technical communities*

Platforms	Objective	Specific goals based on WP8	KPIs
Facebook, Twitter, YouTube and LinkedIn	Raise awareness of the project technologies and build trust in them.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Audiences can see that research used by Project O will solve a societal and environmental challenge in their communities and around the world. ● Audiences can see the scientific excellence and European added value in the water sector. ● Audiences can see that research conducted by Project Ô's consortium members promotes European competitiveness and circular water economy. ● Audiences can see the transnational aspects of H2020 projects. ● Audiences can see the challenges and opportunities of regulatory change in the circular water economy at the European level. ● Audiences can see and understand how Project Ô relates to other similar projects. ● Audiences can encourage others in the technical community to know about and follow best practices. ● Audiences can trust Project Ô's modules and technologies as game changers in the water sector. ● Audiences can articulate a joint vision of a new infrastructure wave in the water sector based on "small loops" and the circular economy. 	<p>LinkedIn: >100 followers</p> <p>YouTube: >100 views</p> <p>Twitter: >100 likes</p>

General, Non-technical Public Audiences

The main objective is to raise awareness of the value of water and the urgent need to adopt circular water systems, as well as to show the benefits of Project O technologies at the demo sites. This will be achieved through content posted on Facebook, Twitter and YouTube.

Table 6. Communications Goals for General, Non-technical Public Audiences

Platforms	Objective	Specific goals based on WP8	KPIs
Facebook, Twitter and YouTube	Raise awareness of the value of water and the importance of adopting circular water systems.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Audiences can recognize and value water as a precious resource. • Audiences can see the impact of the linear circular water systems. • Audiences can recognize and value circular water systems. • Audiences can see the importance and relevance of Project Ô technologies for society. • Audiences can re-signify water reuse, combating its social stigma and developing social acceptance. • Audiences can understand the basic functioning of Project Ô technologies. • Audiences can encourage others to know about and follow best practises. • Audiences can use their knowledge to communicate and debate with their local policy makers. • Where feasible (e.g., in the wake of the events), public audiences will be able to actively share their perspectives with the project and community. 	<p>YouTube: >500 views</p> <p>Twitter: >500 likes</p> <p>Facebook: >500 likes</p>

Project's voice and visuals on social media

Project's voice

We will speak to audiences as people, not as a project advertisement. This means that every post needs to be produced as a conversation. Our voice will be relatable to encourage engagement with a non-technical general public, and clear and open to discussion to engage with technical communities.

Grammar, terminology, and levels of depth of information

The main language for publications will be US English to maximise international uptake and engagement. Following the target audiences' descriptions, there are three levels of depth of information that should be kept in mind when producing content for the social media platforms:

Table 7. Levels of depth of information

Level of depth	Content
General interest (low depth)	What a circular water economy model is and generally the effect it has. In this case, we need to avoid using jargon or specialised terms and strive towards a more clear language.
Policy and Business (medium depth)	Information about the technology on a social and practical level and practical information as to the benefits for using the technology, e.g. savings, PR value, etc. Specialised terms are deemed ok but their use should be limited.
Technical (high depth)	Details of how the technologies work and more technical reporting of facts and figures relating to practical application. Specialised terms are ok.

Post formatting

The length of the text in posts will be variable depending on the social media platform and the content itself. The following guidelines will allow content to be brief enough to be quick to read and to grab our audiences' attention, but long enough to offer some details. All posts should ideally be accompanied by an image or a video.

- **Facebook** posts should be between 40 and 50 characters.
- **Tweets** should be between 71 and 100 characters.
- **LinkedIn** posts should be less than 140 characters (this will avoid the appearance of the "See more" button).

- **YouTube** videos should be between 2 and 3 minutes long.

Hashtag usage

The official hashtag of the project is #EUProjectO or #EUProjectÔ. The use of either one is indifferent since all special characters (such as the Ô) are converted to regular ones to work as one metadata tag. We can also use related hashtags like #ICT4WATER, #WaterReuse, #CircularWater, #WaterManagement, #H2020, #CircularEconomy, #EUFunded, #SDGs, #SDG6, #SDG12, #SDG13 and #RRI, depending on the content of the post. It is recommended to always capitalise the first letter of each word of hashtags to improve readability.

Hashtags can be used within the text if possible. Example:

Figure 5. Hashtags example #1

The #SDGs are 17 goals with a total of 169 targets among them, most of which are meant to be achieved by 2030. #EUProjectÔ will contribute most directly to 3 SDGs: #SDG6 (Clean Water & Sanitation), #SDG12 (#ResponsibleConsumption & Production) & #SDG13 (#ClimateAction) #H2020

Pertinent hashtags that cannot be inserted within the text should be placed at the end of the post. Example:

Figure 6. Hashtags example #2

Last week, the review meeting of #EUProjectÔ was held in Brussels. The fruitful meeting was used as an opportunity to inform and discuss the progress towards the project goals, achievements, deliverables to date, and future project work plan #H2020 #WaterManagement

Visual guidelines

All photographs and/or graphics shared in original posts need to be high resolution images and must be licence-free or produced in-house, otherwise written consent by the author will be needed. The design team will work on design templates intended for different purposes in order to unify all social media platforms' visual identity.

Figure 7. Project Ô logo and colour palette

Content strategy

Key messages

Key messages are the main points of information we want our audience to hear, understand, and remember. They are bite-sized summations that articulate what we do, why we do it, how we are different, and what value we bring to stakeholders. Key messages describe overarching themes, so the potential to create specific messages and combine them is endless. These messages must be formulated in a way that will gain attention and leave a lasting impression. To achieve this, there must be alignment of the message content and associated visuals with the existing needs and interests of the target audience. That is, a differentiated communication approach is required to maximise reach and impact.

Table 8. Differentiated key messages for specific target audiences

Technical communities	General, non-technical public audiences
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Project Ô is a transnational cooperation in a diverse consortium and drives scientific excellence in the water sector. ● Project Ô contributes to European competitiveness and is part of the new infrastructure wave necessary for the circular water economy model. ● Project Ô modules and technologies are game-changers and change makers. ● Project Ô is part of a series of efforts to rethink current water distribution systems. ● Project Ô solves societal and environmental challenges through (not only) innovative technologies (e.g., impact on everyday lives, contribution to SDGs, climate change, etc.). ● Project Ô implements real-life techniques, methodologies, technologies, procedures or participatory processes which are successful and have an impact in specific contexts of application. 	<p>Although this cluster includes different target audiences within each demonstration site that will require specific key messages, these are the general ones:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Water is a precious and finite resource, and we should value it. ● Water scarcity is a human-made problem and can be fought with circular water systems. ● One feature of a circular water economy is to turn what is thought of as “waste” into a resource. ● Circular water systems have economic, environmental and societal impacts. ● Project Ô has developed technologies to optimise how water is used (e.g., processing water depending on the quality required for its next use or developing WWT portable modules). ● Project Ô has developed both water treatment modules and digital platforms in collaboration with local stakeholders. ● The treatment modules are currently installed at four different industrial and household water management situations, and each of the technologies tackle different problems.

Posting content types

Social media posts should be a mix of different types of content. There is a monthly calendar to identify key dates and authentic opportunities to share content from each category that will be updated on a monthly basis based on the results of analytics. This calendar will directly feed to our social media content manager account.

- **Promotional:** Focus on the project itself: technology, actions, demo sites, events, etc. Most of this content will come from the website and be produced by IMI.
- **Curated:** Focus on sharing helpful information (e.g., blog posts, quotes, infographics, best practises, etc.). Most of this content will focus on the concept of circular economy, water sustainability, water reuse and sustainability communication, and will be produced by IMI. Where content ideas / material produced by partners, IMI plays an editorial role in refining prior to posting.
- **Reposted:** Share content from other accounts we follow. Accounts to re-post from must be pre-approved by the task leader.
- **Engagement:** Ask questions of audiences and seek to gain responses (e.g., polls, questions, etc).

Posting frequency

In 2021, the data science team of Sprout Social, a social media management software company, reviewed findings and trends in social media usage of their 20,000+ customers to understand when their content was most and least frequently engaged with, broken out by platform and industry². According to their results for non-profit accounts, the most suitable category for this project, these were the best days and times in terms of levels of engagement to post on each platform. Since the majority of Project Ô partners are located in Europe, the time zone we will use is Central European Time (CET).

- **Facebook:** Tuesday, Wednesday and Friday 9 a.m. – 1 p.m.
- **Twitter:** Wednesday 9 a.m. – 3 p.m., Tuesday through Thursday 9 - 11 a.m.
- **LinkedIn:** Tuesday through Thursday 9 a.m. – noon.

Although determining the posting frequency depends on Project Ô followers' age range, interests and social media habits, there are general frames of reference that can be

² To read the full report follow this link: <https://sproutsocial.com/insights/best-times-to-post-on-social-media/#np-times>

used as a starting point. The following numbers may change over time depending on the results of social media analytics (Section 7).

According to Myers (2022)³, these are the suggested minimum and optimal numbers of posts per platform to maintain a steady level of engagement. This implies that the posting frequency must be balanced or concerns may start becoming relevant: If we post too infrequently, Project Ô audiences will forget about the project; however, if we post too often, we will become a nuisance and audiences will stop following us.

Table 9. Strategy for social media posting frequency

Platform	Minimum	Optimal	Project Ô's goal
Weekly			
Facebook	1	3	3
Twitter	5	15	7
LinkedIn	2	5	2

*YouTube videos publishing frequency relied on the video production plan

Monthly planning calendar to ensure consistency

A monthly planning calendar⁴ will be available to offer an overview of what needs to be published in each platform each day following the content strategy (Section 6.2). It is recommended that the community manager plans all platforms' weekly posts at least one week in advance. Short-term planning will allow us to include emergent information and relevant news.

In the calendar, there will be a tab for each platform (Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn) for a weekly plan linking to the Social Media Posts Database. Each platform will have pre-established times for posts (Section 6.3). Although the community manager will be free to choose the best time to publish from the options offered, the days are fixed and will be determined by the Monthly Content tab.

³ Myers, L. (2022, January 11). How Often To Post On Social Media: 2021 Success Guide. *Louise Myers Visual Social Media*. <https://louisem.com/144557/often-post-social-media>

⁴ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1daQAe-uTvgf-iEB93VTPpqcbYCGvJjUt/view?usp=sharing>

Figure 8. August 2021 Monthly Content tab

MONTHLY CALENDAR							KEY:
							Promotional
							Curated
							Engagement
							TBD
							TBD
							TBD
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
SUNDAY	MONDAY	TUESDAY	WEDNESDAY	THURSDAY	FRIDAY	SATURDAY	
	Facebook - Promotional Twitter - Curated Twitter - Promotional	Twitter - Curated LinkedIn - Promotional	Facebook - Curated Twitter - Curated	Twitter - Curated LinkedIn - Curated	Facebook - Engagement Twitter - Curated Twitter - Engagement		
8	9	10	11	12	13	14	
SUNDAY	MONDAY	TUESDAY	WEDNESDAY	THURSDAY	FRIDAY	SATURDAY	
	Facebook - Promotional Twitter - Curated Twitter - Promotional	Twitter - Curated LinkedIn - Engagement	Facebook - Curated Twitter - Curated	Twitter - Curated LinkedIn - Promotional	Facebook - Engagement Twitter - Curated Twitter - Engagement		
15	16	17	18	19	20	21	
SUNDAY	MONDAY	TUESDAY	WEDNESDAY	THURSDAY	FRIDAY	SATURDAY	
	Facebook - Promotional Twitter - Curated Twitter - Promotional	Twitter - Curated LinkedIn - Curated	Facebook - Curated Twitter - Curated	Twitter - Curated LinkedIn - Engagement	Facebook - Engagement Twitter - Curated Twitter - Engagement		
22	23	24	25	26	27	28	
SUNDAY	MONDAY	TUESDAY	WEDNESDAY	THURSDAY	FRIDAY	SATURDAY	
	Facebook - Promotional Twitter - Curated Twitter - Promotional	Twitter - Curated LinkedIn - Promotional	Facebook - Curated Twitter - Curated	Twitter - Curated LinkedIn - Curated	Facebook - Engagement Twitter - Curated Twitter - Engagement		
29	30	31	1	2	3	4	
SUNDAY	MONDAY	TUESDAY	WEDNESDAY	THURSDAY	FRIDAY	SATURDAY	
	Facebook - Promotional Twitter - Curated Twitter - Promotional	Twitter - Curated LinkedIn - Engagement	Facebook - Curated Twitter - Curated	Twitter - Curated LinkedIn - Promotional	Facebook - Engagement Twitter - Curated Twitter - Engagement		

Reporting plan to evaluate progress

A review of Project Ô social media analytics can be prepared at any point to provide enough information to adjust the social media communication strategy, whether in terms of audiences, types of posts or content. Each social media platform has its own built-in analytics and dashboards (at min. these analytics will feed into final technical reporting):

- Facebook Insights can be accessed by clicking the *Insights* tab in the menu bar across the top of the Facebook Page.
- Once logged in, Twitter Analytics can be accessed here: analytics.twitter.com
- To access LinkedIn Page analytics, we need to sign in to our Page admin centre, click the Analytics tab in the menu and select Updates, Followers, or Visitors from the dropdown.
- Once logged in, YouTube Analytics can be accessed here: youtube.com/analytic